

This supplementary material provides detailed descriptive analyses supporting the global characterization of neoplasms in cats presented in Phase 1 of the main manuscript. All the analyses are descriptive in nature. No inferential statistical testing was performed.

Table S1. Top 10 histopathological diagnoses in cats with neoplasms diagnosed between 2021 and 2024, Colombia.

Rank	Histopathological diagnosis	Tissue of origin	Biological behavior	n	%
1	Soft tissue sarcoma	Soft tissue	Malignant	106	20.8
2	Squamous cell carcinoma	Skin/mucocutaneous	Malignant	81	15.9
3	Mammary carcinoma	Mammary gland	Malignant	59	11.6
4	Mastocytoma	Skin/mucocutaneous	Malignant	35	6.9
5	Lipoma	Subcutaneous tissue	Benign	30	5.9
6	Basal cell tumor	Skin	Benign	21	4.1
7	Lymphoma	Lymphoid tissue	Malignant	12	2.4
8	Intestinal lymphoma	Gastrointestinal tract	Malignant	12	2.4
9	Melanoma	Skin	Malignant	10	2
10	Apocrine carcinoma	Skin	Malignant	10	2

Percentages are calculated relative to the total number of cats with histopathologically confirmed neoplasms diagnosed between 2021 and 2024.

Table S2. Distribution of neoplasms in the cats in this study according to tissue of origin and biological behavior (2021–2024), Colombia.

Tissue of origin	Benign n (%)	Malignant n (%)	Undetermined n(%)	Total
Skin/cutaneous*	62 (23.4)	200 (75.7)	2 (0.8)	264
Mammary gland	2 (3.4)	57 (96.6)	-	59
Digestive system	5 (13.1)	33 (86.9)	-	38
Respiratory system	-	-	-	-
Urogenital system	-	3 (100)	-	3
Musculoskeletal	1 (20)	4 (80)	-	5
Nervous system	-	-	-	-
Endocrine system	-	-	-	-
Hematopoietic/lymphoid	-	15 (100)	-	15
Eye and adnexa	-	11 (91.6)	1 (8.4)	12
Other tissues	24 (18.9)	103 (81.1)	-	127
Total	94 (18)	426 (81.4)	3 (0.6)	523

Biological behavior was classified based on histopathological diagnosis as benign or malignant.

*Skin, digital pad, external auditory canal, conjunctiva, scrotum, lip, nasal mucosa, pinna, prepuce, vulva, and eyelid

Table S3. Distribution of cutaneous neoplasm diagnoses (c-CCE and c-HSA) by breed in cats (2021–2024), Colombia.

Rank	Breed	n (%) c-CCE	n (%) c-HSA
1	Angora	2 (3)	-
2	Mixed breed	62 (92.5)	6 (100)
3	Persian	1 (1.5)	-
4	Siamese	1 (1.5)	-
5	Sphynx	1 (1.5)	-
Total		67 (100)	6 (100)